

MOMENTUM FOR REFORM OF INVESTOR-STATE DISPUTE SETTLEMENT

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Statistics illustrate that around 3.9 trillion in investment is required to fulfill Sustainable Development Goals, current trends showing that only 1/3 of that is reached. To begin with, FDI will be helpful to address environmental problems. “Pollution halo” theory states that modern practices brought to host country may minimize environmental footprint of the legal entity. Besides that, tax revenue generated by FDI, new job opportunities, technology transfer, more output in economy are all essential factors to achieve globally recognized SDGs. From this it becomes quite evident that attracting FDI into country is becoming more important than ever.

What are the drivers of FDI into host state then? The first thing that usually comes to mind is International Investment Agreements that are deemed as main instruments to regulate relationship between host country and foreign investor. One of the reasons why countries are attracted to sign IIAs might be ‘de-politicization’ of investment disputes that provides for international system to which investor can turn for support instead of home country. From investor perspective, IIAs provide some assurance to investors that host state will keep its commitments and they will not suffer from adverse changes in both legal and regulatory environment in country. From the host country perspective, signing IIAs can signal to foreigners about ‘willingfulness’ of state to embrace FDI in their land. As a result, more FDI flows might be achieved. Besides that, in countries where infrastructure investments are a priority, IIAs are also helpful for reducing the need for government securities and international investment insurance.

As for statistics, during 1990s eastern European states experience established great link between investment flows and investment agreements. This happened due to the fall of the Iron Curtain and strengthening of economic ties with western states, which until then was prohibited. Thus, we assume that FDI is important for countries’ economies and BITs, including ISDS is a good means to achieve this objective.

The mission of introducing reforms in international investment dispute resolution system has been taken on by global community. In recent decades, investor-state dispute settlement (hereinafter “ISDS”) has contributed greatly to the protection of investor rights and promotion of foreign investment. Generally, ISDS can be claimed to be successful with an ever-increasing number of resolved cases from fifty-eight arbitration cases in 2020 to sixty-six settled cases in 2021.

Having said that, system is not exempt from flaws, which has been subject to hot debate in this field lately. Thus, UNCITRAL Working Group III has been actively engaged in the reform process. At the same time, ICSID has commenced the revision of the arbitration rules. Some states favor comprehensive reforms, which might include establishment of new investment treaties, investment courts and an appellate system. While some countries believe that the system should be left without systematic changes. Interestingly, there is a third category of countries that would like to get rid of ISDS at all.

So, the question arises as to how much effective ISDS system is and whether any reforms should be introduced? I would like to state interesting analogy drawn by Anthony Neoh to

elaborate the need for change in ISDS system. There is no single person, perhaps, who has never heard about Swan Lake ballet. The legendary play consists of music, choreography, dancing and sets. Glance at historical background reveals that when it was first introduced to the world, it didn't receive such appraisal and honor as it does nowadays. In 1877 first performed in Bolshoi Theatre, with Stepan Ryabov as a conductor, Julius Reisinger as a choreographer and Karl Valts as a set designer, the ballet received a lukewarm reception. Later in 1895, renewed version was introduced by Riccardo Drigo, new choreography by Marius Petipa and sets by Andreev, Bocharov, and Levogt. The sequencing was made easier to follow, music was kept in the two pas de deux- one with the White Swan and the second one with the Black Swan. Moreover, after the performance in London in 1911, Swan Lake entered the world pantheon of the most favorite ballet music of the century. Propelling the ballet into the 21st century was duo of Margot Fonteyn and Rudolf Nureyev with an outstanding interpretation of "Swan Lake".

A ballet has been successful thanks to effective interplay of music, dancers, sets, choreography, each making a contribution to the whole, with the result that the whole is greater than the sum of its parts. In similar vein, today, IIAs that has been signed since the 1960s jointly need the cooperation of all participating parties including but not limited to investors, States, UN agencies, dispute resolution bodies, to maximize effectiveness of these legal frameworks.

Generally, there are more than 3,300 International Investment Agreements including Bilateral Investment Agreements, Multilateral Investment Agreements and Free Trade Agreements. Roughly all of them include arbitration clauses as a dispute settlement mechanism. However, very few of them, only 2% include provisions for recourse for appeal mechanism.

Current discussion at Working Group III of UNCITRAL raises a concern over ISDS system limitations including consistency, coherence, predictability, legitimacy and correctness of awards by arbitral tribunals. The UNCITRAL Secretariat analyzed these deficiencies and included them in "illustrative list" that covers inconsistent procedural rules, inconsistent interpretations of the jurisdictional and admission rules, and varied interpretations of the substantive standards of protection.

At the 36th Session of UNCITRAL Working Group III that took place in Vienna in 2018, the Working Group concluded that introduction of reforms by UNCITRAL is necessary to combat "unjustifiably inconsistent interpretations of investment treaty provisions and other relevant principles of international law by ISDS tribunals."

So, the answer for the question whether any reform should be introduced in ISDS system is affirmative.

Especially, correctness of decisions rendered by arbitral tribunals have been subject to discussion of Working Group:

"On the meaning of 'correct' decisions, it was mentioned that 'incorrect' decisions would be those rendered where treaty provisions have been improperly interpreted by tribunals, not reflecting the intent of the parties to the treaty or contrary to the applicable rules of interpretation. It was also stated that decisions based on manifest errors of law or facts were also 'incorrect', for which there was a lack of mechanism to rectify the situation. It was stated that ensuring correctness might generally assist in obtaining consistency of decisions as well".

It was also noted that currently available post-trial motions such as annulment is deemed to address one of the most crucial deficiencies of the system, which is ‘the integrity and fairness of the process’ but did not necessarily fix the issue of ‘incorrect’ decisions. To remedy this issue, Working Group has offered a procedural solutions including but not limited to creation of appeal mechanism.

Therefore, it will reasonable to conclude that ISDS needs new appeal system to be introduced to tackle one of the underlying issues existing in system- rendering incorrect decisions.

Accordingly, article 28 (10) of the 2004 US Model BIT provides:

“If a separate, multilateral agreement enters into force between the Parties that establishes an appellate body for purposes of reviewing awards rendered by tribunals constituted pursuant to international trade or investment arrangements to hear investment disputes, the Parties shall strive to reach an agreement that would have such appellate body review awards rendered under Article 34 in arbitrations commenced after the multilateral agreement enters into force between the Parties”.

There is also second type of provision in respect of establishment of appellate system in IIAs. Annex D to the 2004 USA Model BIT provides:

“Within three years after the date of entry into force of this Treaty, the Parties shall consider whether to establish a bilateral appellate body or similar mechanism to review awards rendered under Article 34 in arbitrations commenced after they establish the appellate body or similar mechanism”.

However, history has not seen any appeal mechanism being legally operative under any IIA. Thus, legal arena may consider introducing such reforms weighing all pros and cons of it.

Reference:

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4. 2004 US Model BIT